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**ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND SKILL ACQUISITION DEVELOPMENT TOWARDS THE
ACHIEVEMENT OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION GOAL IN OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND
MANAGEMENT**

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ABSTRACT

This paper discussed impact of entrepreneurship and skill acquisition development towards the achievement of vocational education goal in Office Technology and Management. It also emphasized on the concept of OTM as an occupational field of study that boost entrepreneurial development. The paper was able to gather the fact that through Vocational Education, skill acquisition, entrepreneurship education, OTM students can be highly equipped for better life and be self-employed. The paper also viewed the challenges of achieving the entrepreneurial goals through technical education. Further the way forward was discussed and highlighted as follows: NBTE and teachers should take up the campaign for more funds and training centers for vocational education should be created in departments of OTM. Furthermore, it was concluded that no country can favorably compete in the emerging global market with poorly and unskilled labour. Finally, some recommendations were made as follows; there is need to start the teaching of industry-based increased employment opportunities for school leavers of vocational education should be reviewed, and adequate resources should be allocated to business and vocational education.

Keywords: OTM, Technical Education, Entrepreneurship, Vocational Education, Students

INTRODUCTION

Lack of implementation and proper institution of entrepreneurship and skill acquisition among the Nigerian graduates, have left a good number of graduate empty and deficit to the society. Why some who call back to their senses or counselled on the important of entrepreneurship and skill acquisition goes back after graduation to learn trade or to become a craft man entrepreneur from most of the time in the organization of the uneducated. There is no gainsaying that entrepreneurship is supposed to be part of their educational pursuit, mostly in Nigeria a developing country. For this reason, Olariwaju (2022) posited that the Nigerian youth have been denied opportunities to develop in diverse realms of human endeavours. He further commented that there is no image that they (youth) possess than ineptitude, mediocrity and intellectual dearth. This became so obvious and eating cankerworm in 2004 when National University commission (NUC) and Educational Trust Fund (ETF) co-headedly sponsored a national survey of which 61% of 20 organization rated Nigerian science graduates as poor in skills needed in the work environment that have to do with entrepreneurship, technology, literacy, analytical, oral communication problem solving and decision making (Okafor, 2011).

Despite the fact that section 17 and 18 of the Nigerian constitution state that the government shall provide free and compulsory education in order to promote science and technology and eradicating illiteracy for the sustainability of adequate means of livelihood and opportunity to secure employment that can earn a living. All these policies and constitutions, will not hesitate to say that over 70% of Nigerian graduate/youths are useless, deficit and hopeless in the street living the life of crime for survival of the fittest. Formulation of the national youth policy since 1981 and review several times, is full of hope with little or no implementation and achievement. Euewgbara (2017) pose that successive governments in Nigeria since Independence have implemented several programmes to address the problem of youth unemployment, poverty and educational degradation, the assessment of the various contributions of such programme remains abortive compared to the numerous amounts of resources in the nation.

There are so many programmes such as National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), National Poverty Eradication Program (NAPEP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Family Economic Advancement Program (FEAP) among others instituted by the government, but all did not work out as a result of the fact that they have been affected by common problem, such as; corruption, inadequate funding, poor coordination, lack of transparency and accountability. There is no gainsaying that skill acquisition and entrepreneurship development honestly remains the only panacea for developmental enhancement. Fayolle & Linan (2018) posited that entrepreneurship in the recent time have received so much attention owing to relevance in terms of economic development, job creation, productivity and innovation. If entrepreneurship development and skill acquisition are put in place without the involvement of the youth, then it will surely lead to no lasting improvement. No wonder Barinua (2021) says that Nigeria promotes young people to engage in entrepreneurship and regard it as a career option. He confidently says that youths will be a vital source of embryonic entrepreneurship in the future. However, the government of Nigeria have done well by implementing the Kakinada experiment by McClelland in America. This theory according to (Oroka, 2014) that selected young adults were put through a three months training programme on entrepreneurship characters which yielded positive result. Entrepreneurship courses can be made mandatory for all undergraduate students to study. This is part of government goal to inculcate entrepreneurial skill among youths. It is an absolute fact that entrepreneurship and skill acquisition is very important for economic growth, development, job creation and solution to the reduction of youths roaming jobless in the street.

It is a simple fact to note that entrepreneurship and skill acquisition has grown in popularity in industrialized, emerging and developing countries in recent years. Abdulahab (2021) have this to say, that entrepreneurship is usually regarded as the engine that drives every economy. This is because a healthy economy needs a steady supply of entrepreneurship development, skill acquisition and a supporting government.

CONCEPT OF BUSINESS EDUCATION

According to Nwosu (2003) as cited in Utoware (2021), posited that business Education is education FOR and ABOUT business; with the primary purpose of preparing individual recipients for gainful employment or self – employment. This definition emphasized that it gives the recipient the knowledge, skill, idea of been a professional employee and a confident employer of labour. While to Idris (2016) Business Education is education for office occupation, distribution and marketing occupation, business teaching, business administration and economic understanding. From the point of view of Idris, it is clear that business education is a multi-disciplinary field of study.

The vocational business and office education as an occupational field of vocational and technical education aimed at equipping its recipients with knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for them to gain entry level employment as well as advance in their chosen office career or occupation in the face of advanced technological changes in modern offices.

Utowere, (2021) highlighted the following as the objectives of Business Education programme;

- a. To improve personal qualities and building attitudes necessary for adjustment to personal and employment situation.
- b. To produce business education teachers who will inculcate the vocational aspects of business education into the society.
- c. To develop basic awareness of the contribution which business and office employees make to the nation's economy system.
- d. To equip graduates with right skills to engage in a life of work as well as for self – employment.

To produce business education teachers who will stand and so much desired revolution of vocational development from the school level. From the above point of view, it obvious to say that the Department of Office Technology and Management have much to deliver. In office technology, accounting and entrepreneurship, technology and even education.

IMPACT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT

As a matter of fact, no nation grows without building her entrepreneurship career, that to say that entrepreneurial skill is very important in the economic development of every nation. The impact of entrepreneurial skill development in business education can be through entrepreneurship, Office Technology and Management student can be highly equipped for better life. Entrepreneurship inculcates Office Technology and Management graduate, the love for work and confidence in them. Entrepreneurship will help the Office Technology and Management graduates to be self-employed. Entrepreneurship development will affect the society by reducing unemployment. It provides trained manpower in the advance craft and technical levels. Finally, Bongani and Chinaza (2019) Opine that Office Technology and Management students should be encouraged to be creative and functional as entrepreneurs.

CONCEPT OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

Vocational education is that aspect of education in Nigeria that gives opportunity for vocational and technical training. The Federal Government of Nigeria sees vocational and technical education as a comprehensive term referring to the aspects of educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Osuala (2004) views vocational and technical education as training intended to prepare the students to earn a living in an occupation in which success is dependent largely on technical information and understanding of the laws of science and technology as applied to modern design, production, distribution and services. Osuala assertion stipulated that vocational education is a programme designed to prepare individuals for gainful employment as a semi-skilled or skilled worker or technicians. So vocational education is an education made up of theoretical and practical instruction giving to the learners who wish to be employed or be self-employed.

Goals of Vocational Education

The National policy on Education (FGN, 2013) highlights the following as the goals of vocational education:

- a. Provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technical levels;
- b. Provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural commercial and economic development;
- c. Give training and impart the necessary skills to individual who shall be self-reliant economically;
- d. Provide people who can apply scientific knowledge to the improvement and solution of environmental problems for the use and convenience of man;
- e. Enable our young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology;
- f. Give an introduction to professional studies in engineering technologies.

Objectives of Vocational Education

The Federal Ministry of Education blue print and master plan (2001 – 2010) on vocational education noted among others the following pertinent objectives of the programmes:

- a. To produce semi-skilled and technical manpower necessary to restore, revitalize, energize, operate and sustain the national economy and substantially reduce unemployment.
- b. Provide vocational and technical education that is broad based in nature, accommodating all at all periods of life without discrimination or bias on grounds of gender, intellectual tenets and aptitudes, physical disabilities or culture, religion or ideology.
- c. To reform the content of vocational and technical education to make it more responsive to the socioeconomic needs of the country.
- d. Serve as a means of national defense against poverty brought by lack of job skills.
- e. Harmonize and inter-relate with industry and the labour market in terms of resources for training as well as occupation and production standard.
- f. Raise and sustain a generation of job creators rather than job seekers.
- g. Enhance access to vocational and technical education programmes at all levels of education system.
- h. Ensure equity of access, participation and completion rate.

CONCEPT OF SKILL ACQUISITION

Skill acquisition is the ability to acquire practical knowledge in new conditions and on the basis of the abilities and experiences a person had previously (Barinua, 2022). He also posited that skill acquisition is the process of mastering skills characterized by applying them in particular situations. It is the possibility to learn.

However, there are different ways of acquiring skill. According to Barinua (2022), this can be achieved by personal experiments in a certain field, by creative search and constant practicing, and by repeating some actions automatically without implying any thinking processes. Skill acquisition in Nigeria is more important taking into consideration the levels of unemployment. Sincerely saying at a time like this in Nigeria, every youth need to acquire skill for self-development. It is not just enough to be waiting or depending on government in an unbalance economy. It is a fact that millions of youths and even adults of over the range of 50 years of age are still waiting for the government to provide job in a developing country of this kind. It is high time we borrow the words of Abraham Lincoln to say that every Nigerian should think of what to do for Nigeria not what Nigeria will do for you. For this reason, Barinua (2022) opine that the entire life of Nigerians is based on

skills acquisition which is the constant process. It is high time every person will find personal reason for skill acquisition process and results. To Olarewaju (2022), the benefits of skill acquisition include the fact that; it helps you to adjust to the realities of the employment market, you acquire the basis for adjustment for the future needs, it makes you an entrepreneur, other people trust entrepreneurs, so you will be trusted. Experts earn more, so you will earn more etc.

Types of Skill Acquisition

According to Baridam (2009) as cited in Baridua (2022), the following are the different types of skill;

Managerial Skill: In all organization, managerial skills are very necessary for daily accomplishment of the management. Kutzhanova (2009) some functions that serve as tools for the achievement of managerial skills to be; Planning, Organizing, Directing and Controlling if the organizational routines. There is no gainsaying that management of any organization is the major reason while the organization will succeed or fail. Management deal with resource (human and non human) and their duty is working towards the achievement of the organizational goal. The managerial skills create an avenue in which the manager and the subordinate can work together in the attainment of the organizational objective.

Technical Skill: According to Fashua (2016), in Barinua (2022), these are those skills necessary for the achievement of business product or services. It is a fact that technology advancement has taking position in different aspect of production and services which have made technical skill very important today in our technical industry. (Olaniyi, 2015, in Olaniyi, 2022). The ability to apply various technical knowledge in the accomplishment of product and services is technical skills.

Innovative Skill: Innovative Skills have to do with the talent of creating new idea for the purpose of entrepreneurship. Innovative idea according to Urieto (2009), is a combination of one's ability to be creative enough, to solve problem and to possess technical ability. Johnson, (2012) as cited in Barinua (2022).

CONCEPT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

Entrepreneurship Education is no longer new in the contribution of economic development of the country. For this reason, Satya (2019), posited that entrepreneurship education has started taking its, value and importance in the scholarly literature of the countries educational system. Education in Nigeria have started gaining a progressive effect on the entrepreneurial intention and formally chosen entrepreneurship as a compulsory career option of students in the course of study. To Yemini (2019) Entrepreneurship education as an academic delivery is focused on many objectives, of which two are major, creating and increasing awareness related to the positive aspects of entrepreneurship as a career option and conception of understanding the process and procedure of new business creation and skill acquisition. The initiative of entrepreneurship into Nigerian educational system have received much greater significance as it includes gaining knowledge with a process through theoretical understanding and fostering creativity, innovation and self-employment.

However, it is obvious and researchers have shown concern for the inability of some schools to implement and execute pedagogical learning to real life practices. For as a matter of fact it is not enough to render a theoretical entrepreneurship education, rather it is high time for complete practice. To successfully promote entrepreneurship among youth educators and institutions should emphasize more on nurturing various skills required by entrepreneurs. Categorically entrepreneurship education without skill acquisition is dead. The skills required by entrepreneurs according to Satya (2019) are as stated below;

- Technical skills (technical management and organizing skill)
- Business management skills

- Personnel entrepreneurship skills, and above all, should be concrete technical practice of every field chosen by the learner to learn and finally should be summative evaluated.

CONCEPT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT

Entrepreneurship development is defined as a process of enhancing the skill set and knowledge of entrepreneurs regarding the development, management and organization of a business venture while keeping in mind the risks associated with it. (Saale, 2006).

Urieto (2015) Opined that entrepreneurship development is the means of enhancing the knowledge and skill of entrepreneurs through several classroom coaching and programs and training, the main point of the development process is to strengthen and increase the number of entrepreneurs while to Baridam (2014) entrepreneurship development can be define as a process of enhancing the skill set and knowledge of entrepreneurs regarding the development, management and organization of a business venture while keeping in mind the risks associated with it. This can be attained through training programs.

Entrepreneurship development process helps new firms or ventures get better in achieving their goals, improve business and the national economy. Baridam (2014) posited that entrepreneurship has become an important discipline in the present world as more students are getting interested in understanding the important of it.

Challenges of Achieving these Goals of impact of entrepreneurship and skill acquisition in Office Technology and Management

According to Eze, (2013), as cited in Obi, (2020), Office Technology and Management cannot achieve her goal of establishment of skill acquisition centres to raise more entrepreneurship, eradicate poverty, hunger and unemployment, due to the factor it is crippled by numerous challenges. The following challenges among others have handicapped these plans despite all the established body put on ground to support, monitor and evaluate the outcome of this programme.

1. **Inadequate facilities:** most Office Technology and Management departments in Nigerian Polytechnics do not have laboratories or workshop centres, not to talk of having useable equipment and where they exist, they are grossly inadequate. As for those that have laboratory and workshop but left machines like typewriters, dictating machines etc. while for those that manage to have computer systems, no internet facilities, therefore left behind the modern trend of development.
2. **Inadequate Funding:** Odu (2013), as cited in Obi (2020), posited that inadequate funding of Office Technology and Management have led to the turning out of half-baked graduates because there is no fund to provide and maintain laboratory, workshops or even to purchase modern facilities. Well experience skilful teachers may not be employed due to lack of fund. Okoye, 2016) posited that experienced and skilful teachers are or may not be employed due to poor salary do not stay long in the teaching profession but shift to some other lucrative jobs. Furthermore, Momoh, (2012) cited in Okoye, (2016) observed that government lack of commitment to technical education and inadequate funding has weakened technical and business education in Nigeria.
3. **Curriculum of Office Technology and Management:** According to Okoye (2016), the curriculum of a subject with practical content is generally organized into an average of 67% for the theoretical classes and 33% for workshop. The low pace of industrialization and technological growth in Nigeria can be attributed to the widening gap between science, technology and Office Technology and Management as a result of the inability of business education to

adequately utilize the scientific ideas to promote entrepreneurship. This suggests the need to revisit Office Technology and Management curricula in Nigeria.

4. **Government Policies:** Education generally including Office Technology and Management programme has been grossly neglected in Nigeria. Business Educators have the greatest challenges of convincing the law makers on the reason they should give priority attention to the programme in resources allocation. However, it is certain that without the development of technical and vocational education Nigeria will ever remain a technologically backward and dependent nation (Obi, 2020).
5. **Nigerian Value System:** According to Nworlu-Elechi (2013), as cited in Barinua (2022). In Nigeria today too much emphasis is placed on university qualifications not minding whether the holder possesses the required knowledge and skill. But in the developed countries those with technical and vocational degrees are highly regarded. As a matter of fact, the value system in those countries depend on the person's skills and knowledge and not on the stack of academic degrees one has. As a result of this lack of acquiring competent skilful knowledge in the public service graduates of vocational and technical education and business education not left out are often discriminated against and their career prospect limited and underrated for this very reason, secondary school leavers and parents prefer university education to study other professions than technical and vocational education.

PROSPECT OF TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

There is no gainsaying that technical and vocational education is the engine of economic growth mostly in a developing country like Nigeria. No farmer can go to farm without farm tools, so it is that Nigeria cannot develop without well-equipped technical and vocational institutions. For this reason, Dike (2009) says that it is a missing link in Nigeria's development policy. For Nigeria to be out of this mess of millions of youths unemployed, the nation must invest heavily in education with particular attention given to vocational and technical education while business education at the for most as the compendium of entrepreneurship and market. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) and teachers in this area should take up the campaign for more funds for Office Technology and Management and to launder its image in the society. It has been this way in other societies (Ojimba, 2013). It is very necessary at a time like this that Nigeria need to begin to implement policies aimed at reshaping technical and vocational education for effective competition in the emerging global market. According to Okoye (2016), The United Nation Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has noted that revitalizing this sector is among the ways to improve economic opportunities for the youth's development. Also, Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC) and the affiliated Unions could also support at a time like this by setting up an active and functional Vocational and Technical Skill Training Centres in technical and business education departments to operate formal and informal education training for the youths. After these trainings those who perform perfectly in the skill disposal will be established as a motivational strategy. Now is the urgent need for Sustainable Education & Entrepreneurship Development (SEED) and National Economic Empowerment and Development (NEED) to include vocational, technical and business education in particular in their budget for economic growth and development strategies that is aimed at poverty reduction and job creation. Embezzlement, corruption and paying lip service by our leaders in this regard will not solve the problem. Reflecting back to the 1991 World Bank Policy which pointed the development of a skilled labour force as an important factor for the development of any country.

CONCLUSION

As a matter of fact, Education is the bedrock of any developing nation. Education have been the axle for social, economic and political transformation in all the societies. It acts as an integrative force in society, imparting values that foster individual excellence and societal development. Rethinking and redesigning pedagogy of Office Technology and Management is essentials for the 21st century has become very important for educators and policy makers in identifying new elements; the competencies that learners need to develop in skill acquisition and market strategies which make them entrepreneurially developed.

Business educators and all who pass through the technical oriented institutions should be adequately and equitably remunerated. Investment in vocational and technical education and skill training must be given special attention in Nigeria. For this reason, that no country can favourably compete in the emerging global market with poorly and unskilled labour. No wonder Okoye, (2016) noted that Nigeria law makers, stake holders in the education sector need to learn from the international experience as we struggle to establish a more responsive technical and vocational education (TVE) system to meet the demand of Nigerians towards our technological development.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations were made;

- a. There is need to start the teaching of industry – based increase employment opportunities for school leavers of vocational and technical institutions.
- b. The government should also remove the dichotomy that exists between universities and technical institutions.
- c. The curriculum taught in our vocational and technical institutions mostly Office Technology and Management should be reviewed to meet the demand of entrepreneurial development and the market.
- d. Vocational and technical education requires skilled and proficient teachers.
- e. Adequate resources should be allocated to technical and vocational education. This should involve well equipped laboratories and workshops; relevant text books and training manuals be provided.

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